

Combined HEat SyStem by using Solar Energy and heaT pUmPs

Seeking buildings self-sufficiency

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Background

The building sector accounts indicatively for 40 per cent of the energy consumption and 36 per cent of Greenhouse gases emissions (GHG) in the European Union (EU). More specifically, energy consumption intended for heating and cooling represents around half the total of the final energy consumption. In EU households, heating and hot water alone account for 79 per cent of the total final energy use (192.5 Mtoe) (European Commission, 2020a). Most of the thermal energy is produced from fossil fuels (66 per cent), and only 13 per cent comes from renewable energy (Heat Roadmap Europe, 2015). Also, it should be taken into consideration that over 35 per cent of buildings in the EU are more than 50 years old, and around 75 per cent of the EU's building stock is considered inefficient (European Commission, 2020b).

Heating (and cooling) systems have been influenced by, amongst other things, demographics, the efficiency of the building stock, energy availability, energy policies, economic structure, and climate considerations. As a result, final energy demand for heating or cooling varies across Europe.

The EU directives and objectives for the coming years are related to the growing tendency towards smart homes, development of energy-efficient systems and adoption of renewable energy sources and green technologies. Furthermore, nearly zero-energy performance levels initiated by the EU's Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) will bring significant drives in the building sector in the next few years. This Directive states that all new buildings in the EU from 2021 onwards are expected to reach 'nearly zero-energy' performance levels using innovative and cost-optimal technologies with the integration of renewable energy (European Commission, 2019). Well designed and combined systems can improve building's self-sufficiency, energy efficiency and comfort level, yielding significant cost savings, promising payback period and less GHG emissions to the atmosphere.

Project aim

The CHESSE SETUP project objective is to design, implement and promote a reliable, efficient and profitable system able to supply heating and hot water mainly from renewable sources to both new and existing buildings. The system is grounded

in the optimal combination of solar energy production, heat storage and the use of a heat pump in a single system managed by an intelligent monitoring and control system.

The system operation is based on the use of solar panels (thermal, hybrid and photovoltaic) to transform solar radiation into heat and electricity, to be used for domestic hot water (DHW) and heating, as can be seen in Figure 1. During the summer, there is high solar radiation and low heat demand. The unused share of the collected thermal energy is transferred to the seasonal storage tank to be stored, increasing the temperature of the storage medium—either liquid or solid. When the solar radiation is lower and the heat demand increases, a heat pump transfers the heat stored in the seasonal thermal storage at high efficiencies in order to satisfy the energy demand of the building. Part of the electricity produced by the solar panels is self-consumed by the system. If there is an electrical surplus, it can be stored in batteries or injected into the grid.

The operation of the CHESSE SETUP system is optimised according to some external factors, such as energy prices (electricity and gas), weather conditions or user

Figure 1: CHESSE SETUP system schematic.

requirements by using a smart control management system specifically developed for the project. Important to say that this control system is customisable and easily adaptable as needed.

The combination of the high inertia of the seasonal storage system with the intelligent management system allows the energy to be supplied more efficiently and continuously, increasing the self-sufficiency of the system and reducing the peak demands.

The system not only provides a solution in terms of energy efficiency and primary energy consumption but, if implemented widely, could also have great benefits to the electrical grid by flattening the electric curve and allowing greater integration of renewable sources. This could be achieved through the control system, which can activate the heat pump during periods of low electricity demand, for example, or when the grid is not able to absorb the energy produced by renewable sources.

Simulation software

In order to analyse the feasibility of the proposed solution and foresee the results before any implementation or intervention,

it is necessary to perform a simulation of mass and energy balances between the different components. For this, one of the project's deliverables developed software intended to carry out a quick and simple preliminary system sizing. The simulator developed provides an idea of the CHESSE SETUP system performance, and also executes an economic analysis that shows the investment costs, economic savings and the investment recovery time.

The simulator was designed to be user-friendly. We invite any user, with only a little knowledge of solar systems and HVAC (heating, ventilation and air conditioning) systems to run it by consulting the user guide. It is possible to obtain results in just a few hours! The software and user guide are free and available on the [CHESSE SETUP project webpage](#).

Pilots

The CHESSE SETUP system was installed in **three different pilot sites** with different climate conditions, sizing the elements according to the buildings' characteristics such as the solar irradiation, energy demands, and available surface for the installation of solar panels and the thermal storage tank.

The technology is technically easy to implement for new build construction projects, but it can also be used in existing buildings. For this reason, two of the pilots were located in existing buildings (i.e. Lavola's headquarters and Sant Cugat's sports centre). This way (i.e. implementing the solution in both new build and existing buildings) the project also has a significant contribution to the goals of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), in improving the existing building stock, by using an innovative system as that proposed by the CHESSE SETUP.

In **Corby (England)**, with cold weather and lower solar radiation, the system was implemented in 26 new dwellings, including four typologies of homes. For assuring proper exploitation and replication of the system in future developments, it was important to test and monitor the system in several homes, as the user behaviour has a key role in the energy performance. The components of the technical solution proposed for new Corby dwellings are photovoltaic (2.75 kWp) and hybrid solar (2.25 kWp) panels, individual heat storage based in the ground (Figure 2) by implementing an earth energy bank in the form of shallow boreholes (on average 24 per house with 1.5 metres depth), a ground

Figure 2: Corby's heat energy storage in the form of shallow boreholes.

Figure 3: Lavola's rooftop photovoltaic installation.

Figure 4: Sant Cugat's heat energy storage based in a water tank.

source heat pump (3 kW), and batteries (2.5 kWh). There is no backup system.

In **Manlleu (Spain)**, the pilot was implemented in Lavola's headquarters (existing office building, Figure 3). The components of the technical solution are photovoltaic panels (9.9 kWp), air source heat pump (61 kW), and the benefits from the building's thermal mass. The initial configuration of the building contained a natural gas boiler (168 kW) and a chiller unit (118 kW). Both were kept as a backup system in case the CHESSE SETUP could not supply the demand.

In **Sant Cugat del Vallès (Spain)**, the system was implemented in an existing sports centre with more than 6,000 users. The CHESSE SETUP system was implemented in a building renovation at large scale. It is used for heating the water of the swimming pools, being the system very suitable for the energy demand profile throughout the year. The components of the technical solution are hybrid solar panels (41.6 kWp), 100m³ heat storage water tank (Figure 4) and a water source heat pump (97.5 kW). The initial configuration of the sports centre used natural gas boilers (2 x 550 kW) that were maintained as a backup system in case the CHESSE SETUP could not supply the demand.

Table 1 summarises the results of the implementation of the CHESSE SETUP system in the aforementioned pilots. It shows the values obtained as a result of comparing, in a one-year period, the performance of the implemented system versus the performance of the original system using natural gas boilers (baseline case).

¹ The values presented are per dwelling.

	Corby ¹	Lavola	Sant Cugat	
Demands				
Heating and DHW (kWh _t /year)	6,300	67,142	2,398,393	
Cooling (kWh _t /year)	-	19,972	-	
Other electric cons. (kWh _e /year)	3,013	51,197	1,062,222	
Configuration				
Total floor (m ²)	167.1	827	826	
Solar Panels surface (m ²)	32	56	264	
Solar Panels Peak power (kWp)	5.00	9.66	41.60	
Seasonal Thermal Storage volume (m ³)	140	33	100	
Heat Pump consumption (kWh _e /year)	2,440	33,424	25,944	
Seasonal Energy Efficiency Ratio (SEER)	2.6	3.09	4.86	
Savings				
Natural Gas	(kWh _{pci} /year)	7,000	79,364	224,045
	(%)	100%	100%	9.3%
Electricity	(kWh _e /year)	-2,440	-13,930	15,660
	(%)	-56.9%	-23.4%	1.8%
Total energy	(kWh/year)	4,560	65,434	239,705
	(%)	45.6%	47.1%	8.3%
CO ₂	(kWCO ₂ /year)	1,754	18,840	61,138
	(%)	85.2%	65%	9.7%

Table 1: Impact of the CHESSE SETUP system implemented on pilots.

The results show that the CHESSE SETUP system provides a reduction of the primary energy demand (mainly natural gas),

compared to the baseline case. In addition, each building as a whole presents a reduction of the total energy consumption and also a significant reduction in GHG emissions.

Final remarks

The combination of a solar energy collection system (hybrid and/or photovoltaic panels) coupled with the use of a high-efficient heat pump increase the efficiency of the heating system, reducing the demand of primary energy (mainly natural gas) and also reducing GHG emissions of the heating system.

If seasonal thermal energy storage (water tank or geothermal boreholes) is added, supposes the opportunity to decouple electrical consumption from thermal demand, therefore resulting in an important improvement in the self-sufficiency and efficiency of the system. This allows to reduce or displace peak demands in the electric grid.

In terms of the business model, its standardisation and exploitation, CHESSE SETUP was designed as an economical solution, requiring low investments that could be exploitable at different scales. Being a centralised system, it also reduces maintenance costs and energy losses.

References

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From the pilot experiences, we would like to highlight two interesting key exploitable results (KERs) ready to be implemented by any interested stakeholder:

- **CHESSE SETUP system as a technical solution** as referred in the Project aim section.
- **CHESSE SETUP system as a global integrated solution based on energy services**. The solution proposes a standardisation tool as well as a business model analysis for the case studies where energy service companies can play a role. Detailed information can be found in the technical deliverables (D6.2 and D6.4) of the project available at the website.

These exploitable results show that CHESSE SETUP is a suitable technical and environmental solution, as well as economically viable. Strategic alliances with manufacturers, suppliers, engineering companies and interested parties could open the range of opportunities to replicate the CHESSE SETUP model, reducing costs and scaling the implementation of the system.

PROJECT SUMMARY

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PROJECT LEAD PROFILE

The Urban Ecology Agency of Barcelona has been working in this system for more than ten years. Their expertise and previous work developed were a key point to assure the expected objectives. It has wide experience in participating and leading other EU projects. In addition, it is a key stakeholder in the strategic urban planning of Barcelona

PROJECT PARTNERS

The CHESSE SETUP project has been developed by a team made up of: Urban Ecology Agency of Barcelona (Coordinator), Lavola Anthesis, University of Ulster, Wansdronek Architecture, Electric Corby, Wattia Innova SL, Sant Cugat del Vallès City Council, Edenway, Eurogrant GMBH and Veolia Serveis Catalunya.

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